

X3003841.kdpDE

100000

75000

50000

25000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

X3003577.pmr.phosphoethanolamine.transferase

6000

4000

2000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

X3001356.SHV.beta.lactamase

9000

6000

3000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

